

Homœopathy—A pilot study of the attitudes and awareness of pharmacy staff in the Stoke-on-Trent area

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Abstract

The survey was designed to study the attitudes of a sample of pharmacists, technicians and unqualified staff towards homœopathy, and their understanding of the principles involved.

The most significant findings were that the majority of those who expressed a view (i.e. excluding the don't knows) were favourable to homœopathy, but there was little understanding of the subject. Most pharmacists thought that homœopathic medicines worked 'by faith'. An urgent need for an education programme was demonstrated.

KEY WORDS: Homœopathy, awareness; Pharmacists; Stoke-on-trent; Need for education.

Introduction

There has been a steady increase in the number of requests for homœopathic medicines over the past 15 years, with a 50% increase in the over-the-counter market alone in the period from 1988 to 1991.¹ In order to ascertain the potential role of pharmacies in taking advantage of this demand it was considered necessary to identify the attitudes of staff towards homœopathy. The unqualified assistants might be expected to provide a pool of informed, but not expert opinion, with the views of pharmacists and technicians providing an interesting contrast.

In a previous survey the attitudes of pharmacy customers to homœopathy were investigated.² The aim of this pilot study was to consider similar questions with respect to pharmacy staff. British and American pharmacists' perceptions of approaches to alternative health in general has already been reported,³ but here we concentrate on homœopathy alone. A sample of pharmacists, pharmacy technicians and unqualified counter assistants in the Stoke-on-Trent area were invited to complete a questionnaire, and the results were then analysed.

Method

Design of the questionnaire

A questionnaire (Figure 1) was constructed, the questions being designed simply so that a true answer could be given quickly and spontaneously, hopefully avoiding responses which the staff might feel they **should** give. For example, in Question 7, the subject was not asked to consider whether 'treatment of the whole individual' was a possible option, because it was felt that this would require too much thought. Every effort was made to prevent the answer to one question leading to bias in a later question, the emotive issue of drug safety being left until Question 9.

Distribution of the questionnaires

Staff were surveyed in 16 branch pharmacies of a company operating in the Stoke area. The sample comprised 17 pharmacists, 20 pharmacy technicians and 38 unqualified assistants. The pharmacists were all members of the Royal Pharmaceutical Society of Great Britain, and the pharmacy technicians, who dispense under the supervision of a pharmacist, held a qualification awarded by the Business and Technology Education Council.

Questionnaire on Homœopathy

(tick Yes or No)

- | | | |
|---|------------------------------|-----------------------------|
| 1. Have you heard of homœopathic medicines? | ☐ YES | ☐ NO |
| 2. Do you think they are effective? | ☐ YES | ☐ NO |
| 3. Have you tried a homœopathic remedy? | ☐ YES | ☐ NO |
| 4. Has anyone who has taken a remedy recommended it to you? | ☐ YES | ☐ NO |
| 5. Would you consider buying a remedy? | ☐ YES | ☐ NO |
| 6. Would you object if your GP prescribed a remedy? | ☐ YES | ☐ NO |

7. Do you think remedies are effective because:

(Tick any boxes that apply)

They contain herbal ingredients

The idea of 'like cures like'

People have 'faith' in the medicine

A very small dose is used

They are vigorously shaken in preparation

Other reasons

8. Why might you consider taking a remedy:

(tick any boxes that apply)

It would be effective

It would be safe

As a last resort

Other reasons

Thankyou for your help!

FIGURE 1: Questionnaire

In order to exclude bias in the distribution of the questionnaires, the pharmacies were visited over a period of 2 days without prior warning, and without knowledge of staff rotas.

Results and discussion

75 forms were distributed and all were returned.

Question 1—Exposure to homœopathy

The results from Question 1 are given in Table 1. 72 (96%) respondents had heard about homœopathy, only 3 unqualified assistants answering negatively. These were excluded from the rest of the survey.

Question 2—Effectiveness

The results from Question 2 (Table 2) show that 32 respondents (44%) were unwilling to express an opinion, but if these are excluded, the majority (34 or 85%) of those with a definite opinion were favourable to homœopathy. The result should be tempered by caution because 2 pharmacists who believed the medicines were effective, were later revealed to think that this was only because of 'faith' (see Question 7). Excluding these respondents would reduce the overall majority of pharmacists believing homœopathy to be effective to a minority of 7

TABLE 1. Results from Question 1

Question 1: Have you heard of homœopathy?		
	Yes	No
Pharmacists	17 (100%)	0
Technicians	20 (100%)	0
Assistants	35 (92%)	3 (8%)
Total	72 (96%)	3 (4%)

(41%). The proportion of respondents favourable to homœopathy declined as qualifications increased, i.e. none of the unqualified staff were prepared to say that the medicines were ineffective, whereas the ratio among technicians was 3:1 in favour and among pharmacists only 2.5:1. This may be due to the nature of pharmaceutical education which provides for a paradigm that embraces the need for scientific evidence of efficacy before acceptance. Such evidence has been generally unavailable in homœopathy, because double blind trials are difficult to conduct, given the special nature of homœopathic prescribing, although progress is being made.^{4,5} It has been suggested that it is time for a change of emphasis in homœopathic research, so that evidence of efficacy can be presented in new ways.⁶

If the results are tied to age (Table 3) it appears that the over 40 group seemed to accept the effectiveness of homœopathy more readily than the rest (7 respondents, 78%). A similar number of respondents (7) declined to divulge their age. The small number reduces the significance of this finding, however, most of the sample falling into the 16–25 age group. It is normally thought that homœopathy appeals to people in the 35–44 age groups.¹

Question 3—Personal experience of homœopathy

Table 4 shows that although 34 (47% of total) respondents thought the medicines were effective, only 20 (28%) of the sample had actually tried homœopathy for themselves, with pharma-

TABLE 2. Results from Question 2

Question 2: Do you think homœopathy is effective?			
	Yes	No	Don't know
Pharmacists	9 (53%)	4 (23.5%)	4 (23.5%)
Technicians	6 (30%)	2 (10%)	12 (60%)
Assistants	19 (54%)	0	16 (46%)
Total	34 (47%)	6 (8%)	32 (45%)

TABLE 3. Results from Question 2 (variation with age). N = 65

Question 2: Do you think homœopathy is effective?			
Age group	Yes	No	Don't know
16–25	15 (45%)	2 (6%)	16 (49%)
25–40	9 (39%)	3 (13%)	11 (48%)
Over 40	7 (78%)	0	2 (22%)
Total	31 (48%)	5 (8%)	29 (44%)

cists showing the biggest relative affinity. It is possible to relate Question 3 to Question 2, and determine the number of people who thought homœopathic medicines were effective within the group who had actually taken one (Table 5). Among those who had taken homœopathic medicines, there was a greater polarization of views and the 'Don't knows' reduced to 4 (20%). Of the total subgroup of 20 who took homœopathic medicines, 13 respondents (65%) thought them to have been effective.

The favourable opinion of homœopathy among those who had experience of its application was interesting. In other studies it was found that there was no significant difference in attitude between people who had tried homœopathy and those who had not.^{2,7,8}

Question 4—Recommendation from personal experience

The answers recorded in Table 6 show that 60% of respondents were positively recommended a homœopathic medicine by others, and this confirms a previous finding with patients whose main initial source of contact with homœopathy was from friends and neighbours.²

Questions 5 and 6—Consider buying or accepting script for a remedy?

The replies to Questions 5 and 6 are summarized in Tables 7 and 8. Whilst 22 correspondents (30%) would not buy a homœopathic medicine,

TABLE 4. Results from Question 3

Question 3: Have you taken a homœopathic remedy?		
	Yes	No
Pharmacists	7 (41%)	10 (59%)
Technicians	5 (25%)	15 (75%)
Assistants	8 (23%)	27 (77%)
Total	20 (28%)	52 (72%)

TABLE 5. Results from Questions 2 and 3—adjusted to include only those who had taken a homœopathic medicine

Question 2: Do you think homœopathy is effective?

	Effective	Ineffective	Don't know
Pharmacists	5 (71%)	2 (29%)	0
Technicians	2 (40%)	1 (20%)	2 (40%)
Assistants	6 (75%)	0	2 (25%)
Total	13 (65%)	3 (15%)	4 (20%)

only 8 (11%) would resist a doctor's suggestion that he prescribe one, the majority of the latter being pharmacists. This may be due to a wish not to question a doctor's competence by patients, a factor that may not hinder pharmacists as much.

Question 7—Reasons for effectiveness of homœopathic remedies

There were opportunities to give more than one answer to Question 7, so the percentages in Table 9 do not add up to 100. It is obvious that homœopathy is thought to be merely a variant of herbalism, especially amongst non-pharmacists. This may be because a large proportion of homœopathic medicines are derived from herbal sources, or because homœopathic medicines are widely available from herbalists' premises.

25% of the sample knew that a principle of homœopathy is 'like cures like', but the effect of small doses was poorly understood, and nobody appreciated the importance of succussion. In the key areas of serial dilution and succussion, the pharmacists also displayed little knowledge. Almost three-quarters of the pharmacists, a third of the technicians and nearly half the assistants believed that 'faith' played a part in the success of homœopathic medicines. The term 'placebo' was not used in the questionnaire, because it may not have been totally understood by the assistants. This is a common criticism of homœopathy and enjoys widespread exposure.

TABLE 6. Results from Question 4

Question 4: Has a remedy been recommended to you by a user?

	Yes	No
Pharmacists	7 (58%)	5 (42%)
Technicians	8 (67%)	4 (33%)
Assistants	12 (57%)	9 (43%)
Total	27 (60%)	18 (40%)

TABLE 7. Results from Question 5

Question 5: Would you consider buying a remedy?

	Yes	No	Left blank
Pharmacists	9 (53%)	8 (47%)	0
Technicians	14 (70%)	6 (25%)	1 (5%)
Assistants	25 (71%)	9 (26%)	1 (3%)
Total	48 (67%)	22 (30%)	2 (3%)

Many workers have sought to demonstrate that homœopathy does not depend on a placebo effect for its efficacy.⁹

Question 8—Reasons for taking homœopathic medicines

The replies to Question 9 are summarized in Table 10. The purpose of this question was to find out why respondents would take homœopathic medicines. The concept of safety appeared to influence 34 respondents (47%) in deciding to take homœopathic medicines. It may be significant that this figure increased to 21 out of 35 (60%) in the sample with no formal training. Safety with regard to medicine may be interpreted differently and involves the acceptance of a 'reasonable' balance between advantage and possible side effects. It is suggested therefore, that when reviewing these results the word 'safety' should be considered as a variable risk/benefit ratio.¹⁰

The most significant findings were the favourable opinions among those who had used homœopathic medicines, and the worrying view of the large majority of pharmacists that homœopathy worked by 'faith'. A large amount of good quality research has demonstrated that homœopathy does not depend solely on a placebo effect, but unfortunately, sceptics still persist in ignoring this evidence. If the view of the community pharmacists in this group is indicative of the whole country, much work has to be done in

TABLE 8. Results from Question 6

Question 6: Would you object if your GP prescribed a remedy?

	Yes	No	Don't know
Pharmacists	6 (35%)	7 (41%)	4 (24%)
Technicians	2 (10%)	16 (80%)	2 (10%)
Assistants	0	33 (94%)	2 (6%)
Total	8 (11%)	56 (78%)	8 (11%)

TABLE 9. Results from Question 7

Question 7: Why do you think homœopathic remedies are effective?

	Pharmacists	Technicians	Assistants	Totals
Contain herbal ingredients	3 (18%)	10 (50%)	21 (60%)	34 (47%)
'Like cures like' idea	6 (35%)	5 (25%)	7 (20%)	18 (25%)
'Faith' in medicine	13 (77%)	6 (30%)	17 (48%)	36 (50%)
Very small dose involved	0	2 (10%)	4 (11%)	8 (8%)
Shaken vigorously in prep	0	0	0	0
Other reasons	3 (18%)	3 (15%)	1 (3%)	7 (10%)

TABLE 10. Results from Question 8

Question 8: Why might you try a homœopathic remedy?

	Pharmacists	Technicians	Assistants	Totals
Because it is SAFE	6 (35%)	9 (45%)	12 (34%)	27 (36%)
Because it is EFFECTIVE	6 (35%)	7 (35%)	21 (60%)	34 (47%)
As a last resort	7 (41%)	12 (60%)	13 (37%)	32 (44%)
Some other reason	3 (18%)	1 (5%)	1 (3%)	5 (7%)

education. Broadly this is the same conclusion reached by Nelson *et al.*,³ although their British sample was heavily weighted towards hospital pharmacists. Demand for homœopathy will continue to rise for many reasons,¹¹ and it is important to determine the depth of pharmacists' awareness, so that appropriate training programmes can be organized.

An extension of this pilot survey, to cover a much larger sample in different areas of the country, is planned.

Conclusion

Although most of the sample had heard of homœopathy, very few respondents appeared to

understand its principles, pointing to an urgent need for training. Homœopathy is available on the National Health Service, and pharmacists and their staff should have the necessary knowledge to counsel patients and dispense their prescriptions. With training, views on efficacy might well change.

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